

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

PREVALENCE OF OBESITY AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS¹Namra Iftikhar, ²Amanullah, ³Saliha Ayoub¹Akhtar Saeed Medical and Dental College Lahore, ²Rural Health Center Bheikho Mor Mandi Bahauddin, ³Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Obesity is a global issue among the general population. It is also increasing day by day among the medical students. Objective: To see the prevalence of obesity among the medical students of different medical colleges. Material and Methods: 183 medical students from different medical colleges were included in this study. A predesigned questionnaire was served. Data was collected and analyzed in SPSS 23. Results: Out of 183 students, 155 students returned the questionnaire. Mean age of the students was 23.51 ± 1.71 years. 37 students (23.87%) were overweight and obese. Conclusion: According to this study, the ratio of over-weighting and obesity is higher among the medical students so there is a need to modify the lifestyle and eating habits.

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Please cite this article in press Namra Iftikhar et al., *Prevalence Of Obesity Among Medical Students.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06[06].

INTRODUCTION:

Obesity is an abnormal fatty deposition in the body due to certain reasons i.e. improper eating habits, for example, high-calorie diet, non-healthy or sedentary lifestyle and lack of exercise. Obesity if not controlled can impair one's health leading to certain diseases and complications e.g. hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, diabetes and certain carcinomas for example breast or colon [1]. People with a body mass index of 25 to 29.99 are pre-obese, 30 to 34.99 are obese class-I, 35.00 to 39.99 are obese class II and ≥ 40 are obese class III [2].

According to studies, around 1.1 billion people who are overweight and 300 million people who are obese are present worldwide [2]. In Pakistan, obesity is also increasing day by day and is usually found in males and females of middle ages. According to a study, it is increasing due to urbanization, increased economic development leading to changing lifestyle including eating junk food and lesser physical activity [3].

Among medical students, obesity is also increasing throughout the world. According to a study in Malaysia, around 15.9% of students were found to be pre-obese and 5.2% were in obese class-I [1]. Reasons for this increasing obesity rates were the same as found in the general population. Studies from other countries of the world also support this reason [4, 5].

This study was conducted in order to see the prevalence and frequency of obesity and overweight among the students studying in various medical colleges. This study will help us in understanding the reasons for obesity and planning some modalities to control this growing problem.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This questionnaire based cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students of different medical colleges. 183 medical students were the part of this study. An informed consent was taken from the students and a predesigned questionnaire was served. Questions about height, weight, BMI, lifestyle, eating habits, and physical activity were asked. Data collected was analyzed using SPSS 23. Categorical variables were presented as numbers and percentages. Quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

Out of 183 students, questionnaire of 155 were received. The response rate was 84.69%. There were 77 females (49.67%) and 78 males (50.33%). Mean age of the students was 23.51 ± 1.71 years. Mean age

of the female students was 23.48 ± 1.72 years and mean age of the male students was 23.55 ± 1.70 years. 9 students (5.80%) were underweight, 109 (70.32%) were of normal weight, 23 (14.83%) were overweight, 10 (6.45%) were the obese class I and 4 (2.58%) were obese class II. Male and female students according to BMI and certain reasons among overweight and obese were distributed. (Table-I, II)

Condition	Female	Male	Total
Underweight	6	3	9
Normal weight	58	51	109
Overweight	9	14	23
Class I	3	7	10
Class II	1	3	4
Class III	0	0	0
Total	77	78	155

Table-I: Distribution of students according to BMI

Condition	Female	Male	Total
Junk Food	5	6	11
Physical Activity	6	5	11
Family History	1	1	2
Chronic Diseases	1	2	3
Total	13	14	37

Table II: Distribution of students who were overweight or obese.

DISCUSSION:

In this study, 37 students (23.87%) were overweight and obese. Some of the reasons were eating junk food i.e. high-calorie diet and lesser physical activity. There was a history of obesity in families among some students. This picture depicts that a large number of students who are overweight and obese eat improper food and have lower physical activity. This study complies with the results of other studies who aim to see the prevalence of obesity in the general population. In a Malaysian study among medical students, similar results were found. Around 35.9% of the students were overweight and obese [2]. In a study by Chhabra et al. around 13.7% were obese and overweight [6]. Similar kind of studies has also been conducted in Greece, India, and Chicago [4, 7, 8]. This high number of obesity may lead to certain diseases among the students such as cardiovascular studies, hypertension, and diabetes. That may hinder their learning abilities and have a negative impact on becoming a better clinician.

LIMITATIONS:

A small number of students were included in this study. This kind of study should be conducted on a larger scale in order to produce better results.

CONCLUSION:

According to this study, the ratio of over-weighting and obesity is higher among the medical students so there is a need to modify the lifestyle and eating habits.

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